

READING PAPER-BASED TEXTBOOKS IS EASY TO REMEMBER INFORMATION

Abdukadirova Guzal

Corresponding author, the student of Kimyo International University in Tashkent,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Payziyeva Risolatkhan

The ESL senior teacher at KIUT, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

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Abstract. *The research paper's purpose is to identify which type of reading materials, whether paper-based or e-version handouts, are convenient to use for learners when they are the process of learning the English language. The way of using e-books has many advantages in terms of access, cost-effectiveness and easy to carry, however, the experiment investigates that the learners' efficiency decreases when they started to use it. According to the participants' answers of survey, using e-version handouts on phone or computers hurts their eyes, which is considered as a health problem.*

Key words: *paper-based textbooks, e-version materials, handouts, internet, easy to recall, classroom, survey, printed materials, traditional classes, online handouts.*

ЧИТАЯ БУМАЖНЫЕ УЧЕБНИКИ, ЛЕГКО ЗАПОМИНАЕТСЯ ИНФОРМАЦИЯ

Аннотация. *Цель исследовательской работы состоит в том, чтобы определить, какие типы материалов для чтения, будь то бумажные или электронные раздаточные материалы, удобны для использования учащимися в процессе изучения английского языка. Способ использования электронных книг имеет много преимуществ с точки зрения доступа, экономичности и удобства переноски, однако эксперимент показывает, что эффективность учащихся снижается, когда они начинают им пользоваться. Согласно ответам участников опроса, использование электронных версий раздаточных материалов на телефоне или компьютере причиняет боль их глазам, что рассматривается как проблема со здоровьем.*

Ключевые слова: *бумажные учебники, версии материалов, раздаточные материалы, Интернет, легко запоминающиеся, классная комната, опрос, печатные материалы, традиционные занятия, раздаточные материалы онлайн.*

Introduction

Since technology is developing year by year it influences the education system and teachers have already commenced teaching learners with visual supports such as PowerPoint presentations, videos, pictures, and others. Additionally, students have a propensity to read e-version books, magazines, newspapers, and textbooks rather than printed ones which are considered traditional approaches. There are many benefits of using technology devices and electronic textbooks in the classroom. It is greater convenience and easier process in online education for both instructors and students. Students are more interested, engaged, and involved especially in different high-quality activities such as Kahoot, quiz, jeopardy, virtual team trivia, and Quizlet during the lesson. However, according to Clinton, Delgado et Al., robust evidence from three meta-analyses indicate a small performance benefit when reading from paper compared to screens which could lead

instructors to encourage students to use paper textbooks. There has always been a hypothesis that reading paper textbook is more comfortable to learn information than textbooks from the screen. Abaci et Al informed that low-graded students typically do not make good use of and are often unaware of tools afforded by e-books, including annotations, finding reliable materials and video links. This has prompted suggestions for teacher modeling of e-textbook tools for students (Van Horne et Al., 2016). Nevertheless, there is no evidence that modeling would be more powerful than having students read from printed textbooks. The purpose of the research paper is to find out contrast compare and data about paper textbook copies and electronic textbooks on student use of reading materials and to identify which type of textbook is more helpful to get knowledge and remember information. The second objective is to explore the difficulties of using electronic materials and give some solutions to the problems in reading e-version handouts. The researcher in this current study hopes the following three research questions help obtain the objectives.

1. Which materials are better to remember information in education?
2. What are the problems with reading electronic materials?
3. What are the solutions to the difficulties in reading electronic materials?

The study

The topic of research is hypothesis so there are independent and dependent variables in it. The independent variable is the paper-based textbook and the dependent variable is remembering information. The experiment was carried out as the data collection method in this study. A pilot, the researcher, was conducted before data collection, and 9 participants were conducted to collect quantitative data. The 9 participants were selected randomly from KIUT and UzSWLU universities.

METHOD

Participants

The experiment is taken from a group of people, who are of different ages, at KIUT in Tashkent. Participants consist of 10 students, including 9 females and a male. They were chosen from international and national universities. Many participants are third-year students whose major is English education in KIUT and one-fifth are students of UZSWLU. The age participants are about 19-21 years old and there is a graduate student, whose age is 24 years old. In terms of level, most of the students are pre-intermediate and intermediate. Moreover, some of them have IELTS certifications with outstanding scores. It means that they had already been familiar with some readings such as texts, articles, and reports in two formats; electronic and printed materials. The members of the experiment group are monolingual students and speak English as a foreign language. The first language of all participants is Uzbek.

Participants	Level	Study	Age
Abdukadirova Guzal	Intermediate	KIUT	19
Fayziyeva Ruxshona	Intermediate	KIUT	20

Askarkhojayeva Nozima	Intermediate	KIUT	20
Khodjakov Dilshod	Pre-intermediate IELTS 5.0	KIUT	20
Berdiyeva Farangiz	Intermediate	KIUT	21
Gulomova Farangiz	Intermediate	KIUT	20
Gatratova Xadicha	IELTS 7.5	UZSWLU	24
Khaydarova Nurjahon	Upper-intermediate	UZSWLU	18
Umarova Sogdiana	Intermediate	KIUT	20
Komilova Gozal	Upper-intermediate	KIUT	22

Table 1. The data on participants

The table 1 above shows the information about 10 participants. It includes their names, levels, the university which they study and their ages accordingly.

Materials

Two different reading topics in handouts are taken for the experiment from the website “British council” on the internet. This website is the United Kingdom’s international organization for educational opportunities and cultural relations. There are many reliable and cost-effective handouts, articles, and materials in it. The researcher took two handouts that have distinct reading passages with two reading comprehension tasks to complete. The level of this reading text is B2 which equals intermediate level. The topics of reading are similar to each other. The first reading text, a paper printed handout, is about “Work-life balance”, and the second text’s topic which is an e-version handout, is named “Millennials in the workplace”. There are two the same types of task: 5 multiple choice questions and 5 True/False questions in both handouts below the reading text. The total number of questions is 10 in each handout.

After the experiment materials, the researcher used the questionnaire to identify the participants’ difficulties they had faced while completing the tasks. The questions were made on Google Forms which is the fastest form creation. Overall, it includes 6 questions: 5 open-ended questions and a closed question. The questions are:

1. Write your full name.
2. Do you know your result from the experiment?
3. Do you satisfy with your result? Why?
4. What difficulties did you suffer while doing the online reading task?
5. What difficulties did you face while using printed materials?

6. What are the solutions to the difficulties in reading e-version handouts?

Procedure

First of all, the researcher chose participants of different ages randomly, so that the research can be valid. Each of the participants is asked to engage in the experiment formally by sending messages to their emails. Following that, the researcher found appropriate materials and handouts from the website “British Council”. Two reading texts with tasks, which level is B2, were chosen. The first 10 handouts about “Work-life balance” were printed for participants. Another handout’s link was saved to telegram. After preparing materials, the first participant was the researcher who took part in the experiment to pilot the reliability of materials and handouts. The researcher checked out handouts how the level of complication, what the proper level is (in reality, it is B2 or not), what the complication of vocabulary is and how much the reading text and tasks will be understandable for the participants before experimenting. Then the researcher assembled participants to KIUT to experiment. The experiment comprised 10 participants along with the researcher.

The second big stage is experimenting with participants. The researcher asked to announce their names in the research paper or to keep their names anonymous. Then, the printed handouts were distributed among participants. The researcher gave clear instructions on what participants should do. The instruction is to read the text carefully only once, then, to do two tasks (multiple choice questions and True/False questions without looking at the text. The given time for reading and doing tasks is 15 minutes. After completing it, the papers were collected and the second electronic handout was sent via telegram. A sheet of paper was provided to participants. Then, the researcher repeated the same instruction and the participants started to work. The given time is 15 minutes. Overall spent time 30 minutes on the experiment. In the end, all answers were collected and the researcher thanked the participants and motivated them that their participation will be helpful for education.

The third stage is checking results and the researcher informing to participants. After analyzing data collection, the 6 questionnaires were made in google forms and sent to participants to fill out. The researcher set a deadline and waited for the responses for about 2 days. After getting answers, the author started writing a research paper.

Data collection and analysis

All 10 answers in printed handouts and e-version handouts were collected for the analysis of their results. Two comparisons were employed: (1) the result of paper-based handouts was compared with the test result of e-version handouts. (2) the result of the online reading test was compared with the result of the paper handouts. All the comparisons were conducted by using tables and line graphs to see a clear image of differences. The process of analysis took the authors approximately 2 hours to finish computing participants’ results.

Findings

Students’ results

In general, there were 10 students, 9 of them were females and a male. The mean age was 20. Table 2 below represent the students’ results. They used 2 formats of materials while completing reading task. The first is printed handouts and the second is handout on screen.

Participants	Reading test scores in using printed handouts	Online reading test scores
Abdukadirova Guzal	8	4
Kamilova Gozal	10	7
Askarkhojayeva Nozima	7	5
Berdiyeva Farangiz	5	4
Umarova Sogdiana	3	2
Fayziyeva Ruxshona	5	4
Khodjakov Dilshod	6	4
Gulomova Farangiz	7	4
Gayratova Xadicha	8	5
Khaydarova Nurjahon	4	4

Table 2. Participants' results in experiment

As can be seen in Table 2, there is a significant difference in scores between two handouts. There are 6 participants who got higher result than 5 score by employing printed handouts. These are: Participant 1- 8 score, Participant 2-10 score, Participant 3- 7 score, P7-6 score, P8- 7 score, and P9-8 score. However, the result of online reading test shows that students achieved quite less scores comparing to first column. Most of the results are less than 5. Only 1 out of 10 participants got 7 score and two of them got 5 score. The surprising part is that there is a student who had the same score in both reading tests.

Graph 1. The participants' results of experiment

The bar graph is used to describe the results of participants to compare two materials such as printed and electronic handouts. In general, it can be seen that reading test scores in paper-based handout are higher than online reading scores.

Questionnaire

This part of findings is about the questionnaire which was delivered to 9 participants for their opinion on their results, the reason of results, their difficulties while employing printed and e-version handouts and the solutions to the difficulties in reading e-version materials. All participants responded questions.

The first question is about their names and results on experiment. They were aware of their answers before filling the survey.

3. Do you satisfy with your result? Why?

To the answer of this question, 5 participants did not satisfy with their results in both tests. The reasons are that they have trouble with reading skill and they were surprised that their memory is not good enough that they forgot everything while doing the tasks.

Other 4 participants satisfied with their results because they have strong memory.

4. What kind of difficulties did you suffer while doing online reading test?

3 students answered that they had pain in their eyes and they winked their eyes several times so that they could not concentrate.

Other 6 students responded that they forgot the information because they could not underline and highlight key information in the text.

5. What kind of difficulties did you face while using printed materials?

The answer of all participants are the same. They did not face any problems during test. Moreover, they added that they felt comfortable to use printed handouts.

6. What are the solutions to the problems in reading e-version materials?

3 participants gave the solution that they should develop using e-version materials and learn gain their concentration in using telephones.

2 participants recommended to change the device for reading because if they read from laptops or computers they can highlight the main data.

2 students answered that doing some brain exercise can be helpful to develop memory.

Other 2 students thought that they should practice to use electronic materials more because they are reasonably priced and do not impact on education negatively.

Discussion

As apparently seen in all tables of comparing the students' result, the experiment benefited to students to identify which material is easy to use and remember information. The result indicated that the reading test scores in printed handouts are higher than test scores in e-version handouts. It means that even though the online materials are cost-effective, using paper printed materials has many advantages to teachers and students. From the results, it can be seen that the research study answers three research questions successfully. The answer for first question is that using paper-based materials are better to remember information easily and comfortable to use for kinesthetic learners. Secondly, the research paper identifies some difficulties which student faced while reading electronic materials. These problems are interruption, the pain of eyes, not gaining concentration and not having opportunity to highlight key features of information in the text. Several solutions to these difficulties are given in findings part in research paper. These are learning to gain concentration in using telephones, changing the device for reading and doing some brain exercise can be helpful to develop memory.

These results should be taken into account when considering to choose materials such as textbooks, handouts, worksheets and books.

Conclusion

The study of research proved the hypothesis that reading printed materials is easy to remember information than reading electronic materials. The participants of experiment test showed their satisfaction about usefulness of participating experiment, checking their memory and reading skill. They also interested in their results, and waited the analysis of data collection and final conclusion about hypothesis. Most kinesthetic participants started to use printed materials in education, especially in English classes. The research objective was to find out contrast compare and data about paper textbook copies and electronic textbooks on student use of reading materials and to identify which type of textbook is more helpful to get knowledge and remember information. The purposes are achieved and all research questions are answered.

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REFERENCES

1. Chen, G., Cheng, W., Chang, T. W., Zheng, X., & Huang, R. (2014). A comparison of reading comprehension across paper, computer screens, and tablets: Does tablet familiarity matter? *Journal of Computers in Education*, 1, 213–225. doi:10.1007/s40692-014-0012-z [Crossref], [Google Scholar]
2. Cull, B. (2011). Reading revolutions: Online digital text and implications for reading in academe. *First Monday*, 16(6). Retrieved from

- <http://pear.accu.uic.edu/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/3340/2985> [Crossref], [Google Scholar]
3. Duran, E. (2013). Investigation on views and attitudes of students in Faculty of Education about reading and writing on screen. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 8, 203–211. [[Google Scholar](#)]
 4. **Citation:** Clinton-Lisell, V., Kelly, A.E., & Clark, T. (in-press). Modeling E-textbook Tools or Encouraging Reading from Paper: What are the Effects on Medium Choice and Textbook Use? *College Teaching*.
 5. **APPENDIX**
 6. <https://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/skills/reading/b2-reading/millennials-in-the-workplace> (the link of electronic handout)
 7. <https://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/skills/reading/b2-reading/work-life-balance> (the link of printed materials)
 8. https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfAjX_kFmEP9DhXRvqksDIW4f6PfS7IKfo4qNYBqckd0oBxOQ/viewform?usp=sf_link (the link of survey)